

A double happiness before the year ends

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A few days ago, I received the acceptance decision for the paper titled “Kingfisher: Contemplating the connection between nature and humans through science, art, literature, and lived experiences” [1].

The paper reflects most of my team’s philosophies and thoughts about the relationship between nature and humans. It demonstrates how wildlife, particularly the kingfisher, can be used as a connection between humans’ mental realm and natural reality through empirical science, community science, and wisdom.

I consider this paper my best-written article of 2023, so my feeling of happiness was immeasurable when I knew it got accepted.

Amazon Japan, <https://www.amazon.co.jp/dp/B0BG2NNHY6> [1] (Accessed on: 11-12-2023)

Coincidentally, a book by my co-author, Prof. Vuong, which is one of our inspirations to write this paper, also became Amazon Japan’s best seller in the category of humanist philosophy. This is, again, another tremendous happiness for me.

Eventually, it is a double happiness.

Such a wonderful last month of the year!

References

[1] Vuong, Q. H., Nguyen, M. H. (2023). Kingfisher: Contemplating the connection between nature and humans through science, art, literature, and lived experiences. *Pacific Conservation Biology*. <https://www.publish.csiro.au/PC/justaccepted/PC23044>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. (2022). *The Kingfisher Story Collection*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6>